

Curriculum reconceptualization and rhizomatic thinking: Introducing Venn diagrams with Roma students

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This paper through examines how the mathematics curriculum may be reconceptualized through rhizomatic thinking. Students through this process co-shape the mathematics curriculum and create the conditions to acquire meaning through their personal history and their lived experience in a process which is characterized by unpredictable and uncertain events. Mathematics emerges as a useful and practical 'vehicle' helping students to reconsider common sense in elements of their daily lives, to soften power relations, to act towards the restoration of social justice and to lift conditions that are problematic for their personal lives.

Introduction

The internationalization of curriculum studies (Pinar, 2013) encourages post-colonial networks which ignore and challenge dichotomies such as formal/informal knowledge, theory/practice and epistemology/ontology as they engage each other in complicated conversations about mathematics curriculum reconceptualization. A non-hierarchical dialogue among the students and the teacher-researcher may lead to a commitment to forms of knowledge that are not linear but instead have multiple entry points and multitude of pathways which concludes to the need for a rhizomatic approach in research process.

To enact curriculum conceived as a subjectively oriented and historically attuned conversation (Aitken & Radford, 2018; Pinar, 2004) means associating academic knowledge with people involved, teaching not only what is mathematical knowledge, but also suggesting its possible consequences for the individual's self-formation in the historical present, allowing new knowledge to shape the individual's life. In that sense mathematical knowledge in schools should be framed neither with predetermined skills and tasks nor with standardized tests. A mathematics rhizocurrere is thus proposed to create new conditions for successful and meaningful mathematics learning for Roma students.

Mathematics usually act as a key subject which is of great importance in the school curriculum. Many students find mathematics difficult, and some scholars have argued that mathematics serves as a form of gatekeeper by determining social mobility. Relevant research reveals a strong relationship between mathematics performance and the socioeconomic status of the family. (Douglas & Attewell, 2017). D'Ambrosio (1990, p. 23)

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refers to this as the “social terrorism” of mathematics education and links it to the production of negative self-esteem among minority students. Regarding Roma students, they have poor interaction with the mathematics curriculum, and it is very common for them to complete the six grades of primary school knowing only the four basic arithmetic operations.

This paper is part of a doctoral dissertation proposing a reconceptualization of the mathematics curriculum for 3rd grade Roma students in Greece through a post-qualitative inquiry. Research setting is located in the region of Acharnai which is a municipality of Athens and research participants are twenty Roma students who attend the 3rd grade of the primary school. Third grade students are selected because they have started to shape a mathematics class student identity while at the same time negative beliefs about mathematics have not been established yet.

This paper aims at expressing, through the introduction of Venn diagrams, Roma students’ subjectivity. It explores the lived experience of Roma students highlighting underlying links with mathematics academic knowledge in order to portray how the currere, the lived experience of the mathematics curriculum (Pinar, 2013), may replace the planned one. It traces alternative ways of learning and teaching process of mathematics in schools which has the potential to make sense to the Roma students and how students will actually gain voice through their mathematics involvement. Focusing on the interaction of Roma students with mathematics it is proposed an alternative way of approaching the mathematics curriculum reflecting on students’ experiences and practices in various settings which act as sources for the development of mathematical knowledge. Roma students face difficulties related to their schooling in general and there are poor signs of improvement despite the efforts made by educational policies.

Research (non) methodology

Rhizomatic thought (Deleuze & Guattari, 1987) and writing orients the study of social interaction in educational contexts, to the deconstruction of arborescent models deterritorializing, thus, common assumptions that affect the educational process. Rhizomatic thought aims neither to provide a better research model nor to reject the conventional humanistic research but by creating multiple starting points (Colebrook, 2021) it is able to provide new insights and understandings of the ways a mathematics curriculum may be reconceptualised. “There are no points or positions in a rhizome, such as those found in a structure, tree, or root. There are only lines” (Deleuze & Guattari, 1980/1988, p. 8). A rhizome is a non-linear and non-hierarchical network which develops and evolves in contrast to the humanitarian tree and its influence in the field of education.

While researching rhizomatically, educational becoming and subjectivities at the level of people and situations involved, both interact as elements of a labyrinthine and incalculable (Lather, 2016) rhizome which consists of discontinuity, rupture and constantly emerging multiplicities. Research process and rhizomatic thinking have helped the researcher to think the ‘to affect’ and “to be affected” as two sides of the same coin of creating the canvas of a lived experience mathematics curriculum with Roma students. Rhizomatic thinking moves from a unified, conscious and rational epistemology of human consciousness to a relational ontology (Walsh, Böhme, & Wamsler, 2020).

This postqualitative research seeks to “test the limits of our knowledge” by using thinking with theory¹ (Jackson & Mazzei, 2012). Thinking with deconstruction (Derrida, 1967) as the theoretical framework for teaching and learning mathematics with Roma students, permits to work within and against interpretivism during data analysis. Deconstruction is not a method and cannot be transformed into one” (p. 3). For Derrida (1967/1973), a thinker with a method has already decided how to proceed and is simply a functionary of the method, not a thinker. As Derrida explained, deconstruction is not necessarily intentional—it is what “happens” (p. 89)—and categories like the research process, the interview, the field, data, data collection, and data analysis fall apart (St. Pierre, 2018).

During the research process Roma students’ experiences values the context and the social construction of mathematics in relation to the meaning. This paper assumes an ethnomathematical rhizomatic position as a clear political position, because research promotes the preservation of the dignity of Roma students’ cultural group. This political position rejects a colonialist approach which imposes only one way of thinking mathematically and produces widespread educational failure that causes suffering to children. The political position in mathematics education through an ethnomathematics rhizome assumes a respect for the knowledge produced in different contexts, which depends on the historical and cultural funds of knowledge of Roma students. Postqualitative inquiry does not try to measure this experience based on western mathematics, it is all done within the system and has value as such, which is a pure non-colonialist practice.

Intercultural orientation stands as an element of the quality of pedagogical practices (Abacioglu et al., 2020; Stathopoulou et al., 2012). The ethnomathematical rhizome as a pedagogical and philosophical act is basically an act open to the future development of children, which takes into account the current cultural and learning funds of knowledge of the child but remains open to the elements of the unpredictable, spontaneous and authentic logic. In that sense, the interculturally oriented curriculum development should use the different cultural and linguistic aspects that Roma students bring with them in order to strengthen their individual cognitive and socio-emotional development.

Postqualitative inquiry’s immanence (St. Pierre, 2019) makes the research not to systematically repeat a preexisting research, reprocess to produce a recognizable result, but to experiment and offer something new and different that “might not be recognizable in existing structures of intelligibility” (St. Pierre, 2018). Deleuze (1968/1994, p. 136) explains that the thoughts and practices considered as authority of knowledge should be treated “every time as something which has not always existed, but begins, forces and under constraint”. Research design in this case does not have pre-formed questions and methodology as the field under study unfolds in front of the researcher while experimenting, creating, becoming and re-orienting thought. Researcher’s identity is shaped simultaneously with the research process.

¹ Jackson & Mazzei (2017) situate thinking with theory, “not as a method with a script but as a new analytic for qualitative inquiry. Every truth, Deleuze (1983) wrote, is of a time and a place; thus, we work within and against the truths of humanist, conventional, and interpretive forms of inquiry and analysis that have centered and dominated qualitative research texts and practices. We proceed with hesitation and a sense of instability, because as readers will see, there is no formula for thinking with theory: It is something that is to come; something that happens, paradoxically, in a moment that has already happened; something emergent, unpredictable, and always rethinkable and redoable” (p. 717).

In practice, the researcher approaches the subject through experimentation and lived experience, leaving open implications for new things that may arise in the process. The discursive breadths that result from lived experience are treated with transcendental empiricism but are not intended to establish universal truth about the process. The change takes place simultaneously with the research and the validity is developed through the eyes of the participants who experience the change in their daily practice. New ways of thinking can emerge through engaging with mathematical concepts, bringing about long-term and short-term changes in the daily lives of Roma students. Deleuze (1990/1995) suggests “never interpret experience and experiment (p. 87)” giving emphasis on the creative character of the research which is open to new “becomings” that seek to shape how both participants and the researcher are “becoming” in the assemblages of the research.

Research (non) data

Quite often students discuss to determine the relationship between them. The kind of relationships between them is a constant topic of discussion. They also discuss how these relationships arise through their family’s history and their family tree. In order to illustrate these kinship relations in a tangible way, we decided to negotiate the Venn diagrams in collaboration with the students. First, the children were presented with an image of items that can be purchased from a grocery store and items that can be purchased from a greengrocer. Thus, two distinct sets of objects were formed, but also some objects emerged that exist in both stores. These objects are written at the intersection of the two sets.

Picture 1: Representing family tree through Venn diagrams

In order for the students to understand the meaning of the intersection and the union of the sets, they were presented with a simple diagram, which consists of all the relatives of the father and all the relatives of the mother. The intersection of these two sets includes the students themselves as well as their siblings. Students, after extensively completing their parents’ family members, understand the essence of the Venn diagram, their practical utility in depicting their family relationships, and discover family members belonging to both groups.

In the discussions that take place in this context, Evangelia wonders “My father has one or two second cousins (brothers among themselves) one of whom has married my mother’s sister and the other has married my mother’s first cousin. Will their children be enrolled in both circles?”

Spyros states, “My father and mother are somewhat related. That is, my grandfather’s brother adopted my mother. Nevertheless, they are not of the same blood. Shouldn’t my parents belong to both circles as we children do?” At the same time, cultural issues emerge as the rest of the students realize that it is not “correct” to report publicly their family’s incest issues. Students, thus, are beginning to hide those written in the intersection of the two sets in the Venn diagram by erasing some names.

Picture 2: Identifying persons who belong to the intersection

Picture 3: Thoughts about sex discrimination

This mathematics task gives children the opportunity to realize incest issues that concern their families, to consider whether it is right or not that this happens and whether they should reveal their family's secrets during the lesson. It is common in Roma society for marriages to take place in a closed circle. This certainly does not happen because the Roma do not want to alter their race as the prevailing view claims. In reality, the cause is that the prevailing culture avoids associating with them, thus leading to their marginalization and isolation as a group (Ciaian & Kancs, 2019). Consequently, teenagers in Roma community get usually married at the age of fourteen.

Zoe reports, "My godfather has married my mother's first cousin. My godfather has my father as his first cousin but I will not write him in the middle. I will write my godfather, without you knowing that he is my father's cousin. Because if they see it, they will kill me because I told tales about it". Katerina (who is a child with older sisters who have dropped out of school at the age of 12 in order to get married) makes a Venn diagram with the differences between boys and girls. At the intersection of the two sets there are the phrases "girls and boys are smart, they both go to school". In other words, we realize that the child is overwhelmed by thoughts about gender discrimination between boys and girls. Venn diagrams and mathematics become the occasion for her to be able to externalize these thoughts and to support her own point of view, that is, equality between boys and girls, in a more formal way.

Vasilis thinks directly about the similarities and differences that exist between their own tribe (Romanian-Vlachs or Rundarides) and the competing Roma group (Chalkidians) that exist in the same area noting as difference that "they steal, they live in dirty houses" while in the similarities he states that "they also go to school and believe in God". School and education therefore receive universal dimensions and are a common experience even for groups of people with conflicting interests. Education seems to bridge the gaps between rival social groups and be a common starting point for reconciliation.

Lakis continues to think about the research topic and he suggests comparing the hobbies that existed in past and today. He finds that the most important difference between the present and the past is the existence of electronic games and the internet. Considering similarities, he mentions the children's games such as hide and seek as well as hunting because "children always want to play in the countryside". He also mentions "In several countries some learn English, some German, some Greek but everyone does arithmetic (meaning Mathematics) because the numbers are the same for everyone. Everyone sells,

buys, counts and makes transactions”. In other words, the student recognizes the universal dimension of mathematics, that mathematics is potentially a universal language of communication that unites rather than separates people, cultures and civilizations.

The above mentioned (non) data provide excuses that mathematics can become a vehicle for social improvement through occasions which permit re-examining individual’s history and the historic present. A culturally oriented version of Venn diagrams for Roma students who identify applications of Venn diagrams in their real life illustrates an example of the mathematics rhizocurrere which challenges the idea of who can do mathematics. At the same time, they touch on issues of their recent personal and family history as well as issues of racial discrimination and gender issues. Such an approach to the mathematics curriculum creates discursive plateaus, which create the opportunity for personal human stories to emerge exposing teachers and students as producers of mathematics knowledge.

Conclusions

Rather than seeking a single, unified truth working according to an arboreal model of knowledge, this rhizocurrere promotes recognition of the contingent and temporary nature of what is discovered at those nodal meeting points. It also highlights that new knowledge moves in new, often unpredictable, directions, examining where our thinking may move along lines of flight. In effect, this alternative model acts as a canvas to try out new combinations of ideas. Thus, rhizomatic research culture is characterized by heterogeneity, multiplicity, proliferation, flexibility, non-linearity, connection and non-hierarchical networks.

This paper does not focus on identifying the truth of the Roma students but following Jackson’s and Mazzei’s (2012, p. 5) proposal, the research “is deliberate and transparent in what analytical questions are made possible by a specific theoretical concept and how the questions that we used to think with did not precede our analytic practice (as research questions might) but emerged in the middle of “plugging in”.

The purpose of the paper is to create new discourse about the experiences of Roma students which may be related to mathematics and are powerful enough to turn the traditional mathematics curriculum into a vivid currere giving new impetus to the whole learning process. The research is not leveling in terms of developing conclusions that apply to all participants but reveals dimensions of living experiences, differences in way of thinking and living. Kumm and Berbary (2018) mention that “post-inquiry, as becoming, is often left open-ended or spilling over”.

A teacher who applies the rhizome approach to an intercultural classroom will have the advantage of co-creating a teaching plan with his students that meets their particular (cultural, social and learning) needs which are not always clear in advance. In order to assess whether, on the one hand, the concepts of mathematics knowledge and, on the other, the deconstruction of student prejudices and common-sense imperialism have been achieved towards restoration of social justice. Dignity, recognition and reconciliation coexist as a transformation of and with coloniality rather than simply perpetuating it (Appelbaum, 2019). Mathematics becomes a tool for understanding the world that supports critical thinking and analysis. Roma students’ interaction in the mathematics framework both with other students and the wider community creates alternative extensions on how students understand mathematics, themselves and how their world may be explored mathematically.

Curriculum reconceptualization and rhizomatic thinking

Figure 1: The rhizomatic development of the mathematics curriculum

This paper promotes a different view of mathematics curriculum through emerging contexts and relationships which show community’s interests of what mathematics learning could be and develops students’ experiences in connection with daily realities students face. The proposed rhizocurrere ensures that Roma students have access to mathematics in their ‘language’. Although Roma students usually achieve poor mathematics knowledge, when a mathematics curriculum co-shaping process embodies their experiences ensuring thus their active participation, the learning outcomes become impressive.

The student’s real education emerges when they are able to find ways to integrate individual issues by relating them to everyday life, in order to later continue self-regulated learning in the context of lifelong learning. Teachers through the development of such a rhizocurrere, pay special attention to the procedural side of knowledge, constantly updating their methods and leading students to unexpected cognitive fields arising from daily practice. Students develop a research culture trying to identify mathematics in situations which initially do not seem mathematical. They also develop critical thinking which will contribute to the creation of a better world through respect, understanding of intercultural differences and taking action as a consequence of their education.

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